

An examination of scientific collaboration between Taiwan and New Southbound Policy target countries

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Abstract

The New Southbound Policy (NSP) is generally considered a grand strategic plan for Taiwan to diversify its economy and reintegrate itself into the Indo-Pacific region in response to the changing global and regional geopolitics by fostering long-term partnerships with 18 neighboring countries. Promoting regional academic cooperation is part of resource sharing but receives little scholarly discussion. To better understand the collaboration pattern between Taiwan and NSP target countries, we describe five collaboration behaviors based on the Probability Affinity Index (PAI) and Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA): co-opt, solidarity, master–pupil (TWN-led or NSP-led), and non-preferred. The study finds that solidarity is the most prevalent collaboration behavior between Taiwan and eight NSP priority countries across 14 disciplines, whereas collaboration with non-priority countries is predominantly non-preferred or non-existence. Furthermore, collaboration behavior is highly correlated with the resemblance of cross-specialization scientific profiles, with countries in the same cluster as Taiwan exhibiting collaborations between equals. The collaboration moves into master–pupil behavior as the profiles get increasingly dissimilar. This study highlights the heterogeneities in collaboration not fully captured by well-recognized factors such as physical distance, income level, and science & technology capacity.

Introduction

The increasingly heated competition between the U.S. and China in every aspect, including science and technology, has rekindled researchers' attention to the role of nations and the impact of geopolitics in international collaboration (Wagner & Cai, 2022). Prior studies have pointed to historical and geopolitical factors in shaping patterns of international collaboration but are mostly Western-centric (Luukkonen, Persson & Sivertsen, 1992; Okubo, Miquel, Frigoletto & Doré, 1992; Zitt, Bassecoulard & Okubo, 2000). This study focuses instead on Taiwan and its scientific collaboration with neighboring countries under new policy initiatives aiming to strengthen regional partnerships in response to the changing regional and global geopolitics.

The New Southbound Policy (NSP), proposed by Taiwan's President Tsai Ing-Wen in 2016, is generally considered a grand strategic plan to not only invigorate and diversify Taiwan's economy but also redefine Taiwan's role in regional development. Guided by the principle of forging a “sense of economic community” and forming (Office of the President, Republic of China (Taiwan), 2016) a “consensus for cooperation,” its implementation plan highlighted (1) economic and trade cooperation, (2) talent exchange, (3) resource sharing, and (4) regional connectivity among 18 target countries in Southeast and South Asia, as well as Oceania. Given historical, geocultural affinities and strategic importance, eight are designated as priority countries, including India, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Thailand, Vietnam, Singapore, and Australia. In response, National Science Council (NSC) launched the New Southbound Science & Technology Cooperation (NSSTC) Project Office in the same year to (1) promote

regional academic cooperation, (2) promote talent exchange and cultivation, (3) build international collaboration platform, and (4) connect international science parks under the guiding principle of “solving common problems and creating mutual benefits” (MOST Center for Global Affairs and Science Engagement, 2020).

While there have been a handful of publications on the NSP since its conception, the potential and actual impact of NSP on scientific collaboration and mobility has received little scholarly discussion outside (semi-)government agencies. Lee and Chiu (2018) pointed to the four challenges of NSC in promoting science & technology cooperation with NSP target countries, with the lack of understanding and genuine interest in the local affairs in Southeast and South Asia being one of them. Corresponding policy recommendations from the “science diplomacy” perspective encourage collaboration in problem-oriented research. Another collection of work edited by Chen (2019) provides a high-level, largely descriptive overview of potential areas of bilateral collaboration with NSP target countries in scientific and technological innovation within the “innovative growth partnership” framework. Although both reports are valuable resources for researchers and practitioners, there are few empirical studies to engage in the continuing the dialogues with this policy initiative and evaluate its effectiveness.

The present study aims to fill the empirical gap by looking into the bilateral collaboration behavior between Taiwan and 18 NSP partners based on their association strength and comparative advantage across 14 disciplines.

Data and methods

Data for this paper is based on Clarivate Analytics’ Web of Science, curated at the Observatoire des sciences et des technologies. Analysis is based on two datasets extracted from the database. The first is a high-level overview of publication counts by country, year, and discipline. The other is an edge list of the number of co-authored papers between the two countries, aggregated by year and discipline. While the data cover the period 1980–2021, for the current study, we focus only on publication activity between 2017 and 2020. There are 14 disciplines under the National Science Foundation (NSF) classification: Arts, Biology, Biomedical Research, Chemistry, Clinical Medicine, Earth and Space, Engineering and Technology, Health, Humanities, Mathematics, Physics, Professional Fields, Psychology, and Social Sciences.

Following the research design of Zitt et al. (2000), we calculated the Activity Index (AI) and Probabilistic Affinity Index (PAI) to understand the bilateral collaboration behaviors between Taiwan and NSP target countries. The AI characterizes the relative research effort a country devotes to a given discipline and is equivalent to Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) (cf. Miao et al., 2022), whereas PAI reveals the strength of association between two countries in collaboration on a global scale after controlling for the size of both countries. A country c is considered to have comparative advantage in discipline i if $\log_{10}RCA_{c,i} > 0$. Two countries a, b are considered preferred partners for each other in discipline i if $PAI_{a,b,i} > 0$ after normalizing to $[-1,1]$.

Five collaboration behaviors were derived between Taiwan and NSP target countries on the basis of Zitt et al. (2000):

- Co-opt (strong–strong): Preferred partnership in discipline i where both have comparative advantage (1st quadrant)
- Solidarity (weak–weak): Preferred partnership in discipline i where neither have comparative advantage (3rd quadrant)
- Master–pupil behavior (strong–weak)
 - TWN-led: Preferred partnership in discipline i where only Taiwan has comparative advantage (4th quadrant)

- NSP-led: Preferred partnership in discipline i where only NSP target country has comparative advantage (2nd quadrant)
- Non-preferred: Non-preferred partnership in discipline i regardless of revealed comparative advantage

Informed from prior studies, we also included income level (Serajuddin & Hamadeh, 2020), both 2001 and 2018 versions of the Science and Technology Capacity Index (STCI) (Wagner, 2022; Wagner, Brahmakulam, Jackson, Wong & Yoda, 2001), as well as the physical distance between capitals of Taiwan and NSP target countries as potential explanatory factors for the perceived patterns (Table 1). The distance between the two capitals was obtained from an R package “peacesciencer” (Miller, 2022). Finally, we calculated the χ^2 distance between countries and applied hierarchical clustering with the “ward.D2” method to identify potential clusters in terms of their cross-specialization profiles.

Table 1. Overview of the NSP target country profiles.

<i>Code</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Capital</i>	<i>Income Level</i>	<i>STCI 2001</i>	<i>STCI 2018</i>	<i>Distance</i>
TWN	Taiwan	Taipei	H	SAC	SAC	–
<i>Southeast Asia</i>						
PHL	Philippines	Manila	LM	SLC	SLC	1,164.52
VNM	Viet Nam	Hanoi	LM	SLC	SLC	1,668.80
LAO	Lao People’s Democratic Republic	Vientiane	LM	SLC	SLC	2,111.97
KHM	Cambodia	Phnom Penh	LM	SLC	SLC	2,306.58
BRN	Brunei Darussalam	Bandar Seri Begawan	H	SLC	SDC	2,351.85
THA	Thailand	Bangkok	UM	SLC	SDC	2,538.62
MMR	Myanmar	Pyinmana	LM	SLC	SLC	2,671.13
MYS	Malaysia	Kuala Lumpur	UM	SLC	SPC	3,235.44
SGP	Singapore	Singapore	H	SPC	SAC	3,257.39
IDN	Indonesia	Jakarta	LM	SDC	SLC	3,823.70
<i>South Asia</i>						
BGD	Bangladesh	Dhaka	LM	SLC	SLC	3,153.44
BTN	Bhutan	Thimphu	LM	SLC	SDC	3,190.59
NPL	Nepal	Kathmandu	LM	SLC	SLC	3,614.06
IND	India	New Delhi	LM	SPC	SDC	4,399.46
PAK	Pakistan	Islamabad	LM	SDC	SLC	4,759.16
LKA	Sri Lanka	Colombo	LM	SLC	SLC	4,868.51
<i>Oceania</i>						
AUS	Australia	Canberra	H	SAC	SAC	7,316.24
NZL	New Zealand	Wellington	H	SPC	SAC	9,197.41

Note: Shaded rows indicate priority countries. Income level: H=High (>12,535), UM=Upper-middle (4,046–12,535), LM=Lower-middle (1,036–4,045). STCI: SAC=Advanced, SPC=Proficient, SDC=Developing, SDC=Lagging. The original score of STCI 2018 was converted into four categories based on the following criteria: SAC (above 90 percentiles), SPC (75–90 percentiles), SDC (50–75 percentiles), and SLC (below 50 percentiles).

Results

Of 252 possible collaboration ties between Taiwan and NSP target countries across disciplines, half are in a preferred partnership, 23% are non-preferred, and the remaining 27% are not in a partnership at all. Unlike the commonly held notion of co-opt behavior as the prevailing pattern of collaboration (Zitt et al., 2000), preferred partnership is more likely to exist in disciplines where both countries are weak (i.e., solidarity; 31.7%) or where only NSP target countries have comparative advantage (i.e., NSP-led; 32.5%). Nevertheless, the difference between preferred and non-preferred partnership across four quadrants is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($\chi^2 = 7.15, df = 3, p = 0.06$). There is thus no

evidence to suggest that Taiwan is not a partner of high priority in disciplines where it has comparative advantage, including Professional Fields, Engineering and Technology, Mathematics, Chemistry, and Physics. The difference in collaboration behavior is statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 58.142, df = 5, p < 0.001$) depending on the priority status of NSP target countries. A plurality of non-priority countries has no collaboration ties (41.4%), and less than a third are preferred partners across 14 disciplines. In contrast, solidarity is the most prevalent collaboration behavior between Taiwan and priority countries (27.7%), only distantly followed by NSP-led (18.8%), co-opt (15.2%), and Taiwan-led (12.5%), although non-preferred also accounts for 17% (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of collaboration behaviors within priority and non-priority countries.

<i>Collaboration behavior</i>	<i>Non-priority country</i>	<i>Priority country</i>	<i>Total</i>
Co-opt	5 (3.6%)	17 (15.2%)	22 (8.7%)
TWN-led	9 (6.4%)	14 (12.5%)	23 (9.1%)
Solidarity	9 (6.4%)	31 (27.7%)	40 (15.9%)
NSP-led	20 (14.3%)	21 (18.8%)	41 (16.3%)
Non-preferred	39 (27.9%)	19 (17.0%)	58 (23.0%)
None	58 (41.4%)	10 (8.9%)	68 (27.0%)
Total	140 (100.0%)	112 (100.0%)	252 (100.0%)

Results from hierarchical clustering yielded three distinct clusters: (A) Brunei, Taiwan, Singapore, Vietnam, India, Malaysia, and Pakistan; (B) Australia, New Zealand, Thailand, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, and Indonesia; (C) Cambodia, Nepal, Philippines, Bhutan, Lao, and Myanmar. The cluster (A) to which Taiwan belongs is characterized by a much higher share of publications in Engineering & Technology (27.3% vs. 17.7%) and a lower share of Clinical Medicine (15.5% vs. 24.1%) compared to the world average. The cluster (C) furthest away is formed primarily by lower-middle, scientifically lagging countries with significant concentrations in Clinical Medicine (32.2% vs. 24.1%) and Biology (20.4% vs. 7.1%) but a striking dearth of Engineering & Technology (4.7% vs. 17.7%). In the middle is the cluster (B) balancing in between, with a slightly lower share in Engineering & Technology (14.1% vs. 17.7%) and Clinical Medicine (22.8% vs. 24.1%) but a higher share in Biology (13.4% vs. 7.1%) than the world average (Table 3).

Table 3. Mean cross-disciplinary share of scientific publications for resulting clusters.

<i>Discipline</i>	<i>Cluster A</i>	<i>Cluster B</i>	<i>Cluster C</i>	<i>World Average</i>
Clinical Medicine	0.155	0.228	0.322	0.241
Engineering and Technology	0.273	0.141	0.047	0.177
Biomedical Research	0.105	0.129	0.144	0.124
Chemistry	0.093	0.058	0.018	0.081
Earth and Space	0.088	0.095	0.102	0.081
Physics	0.085	0.058	0.015	0.076
Biology	0.080	0.134	0.204	0.071
Social Sciences	0.026	0.038	0.044	0.032
Mathematics	0.031	0.016	0.006	0.030
Professional Fields	0.031	0.038	0.020	0.028
Health	0.018	0.039	0.065	0.025
Psychology	0.008	0.016	0.007	0.019
Humanities	0.005	0.008	0.005	0.013
Arts	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002

By ordering countries according to their cluster assignments, it can be clearly seen from Figure 1A that countries in resemblance to Taiwan tend to collaborate with Taiwan in disciplines either equally strong or weak (i.e., collaboration between equals) such as Singapore, Malaysia, India, and Vietnam. Conversely, countries dissimilar to Taiwan are more likely to collaborate in disciplines with complementary advantages—the Philippines being an excellent exemplar. The same figure can also infer possible reasons for non-preference in collaboration and the lack thereof. On the one hand, non-preference is likely to be a function of geographic distance, as best illustrated by Australia and New Zealand, despite both having the same income and S&T capacity levels as Taiwan. On the other hand, the lack of collaboration may have more to do with the low S&T capacity of partner countries, often in tandem with the least similar scientific profiles to Taiwan.

In terms of disciplines, the most distinct pattern is the unanimous NSP-led collaboration in Biology and a lack of collaboration in Arts across NSP target countries. Clinical Medicine is another discipline with intensive collaboration, where solidarity is the predominant behavior within priority countries but tied with NSP-led within non-priority countries. Among disciplines where Taiwan has a comparative advantage, Engineering & Technology, Chemistry, and Professional Fields are primarily co-opt within priority countries, while Math is led by Taiwan. The case of Physics is interesting in that both priority and non-priority countries share a similar pattern of indistinctiveness, together making it another TWN-led discipline in collaboration (Figure 1B).

Figure 1. Collaboration behavior across (A) NSP target countries, ordered by the χ^2 distance to Taiwan in terms of scientific publication profiles within clusters (color-coded) and (B) disciplines, faceted by priority status.

Discussion and conclusion

Current analyses justify the rationale for prioritizing certain countries in policy implementation, although the overall non-preferred partnership with Australia showcases both the limits of policy and complicated factors shaping scientific collaboration. Another distinction in Taiwan's

scientific collaboration with NSP priority countries is that solidarity—rather than co-opt—is the most common pattern, especially in Clinical Medicine and Biomedical Research. While solidarity in these two fields may be to some extent an indication of “solving common problems,” it also serves as caution for Taiwan’s authorities who tend to assume scientific superiority in these fields. Even among disciplines where Taiwan has comparative advantages, like Engineering & Technology and Chemistry, Taiwan is seldom a leader but is in equal partnership with priority countries and not even preferred among non-priority countries. Finally, the clustering results of countries based on their cross-specialization show great heterogeneity across income levels and S&T capacity. Even among the four countries with both high income and advanced S&T capacity, Taiwan and Singapore have scientific profiles that are quite different from those of Australia and New Zealand. While these development-based measures remain important in characterizing collaboration patterns, similarities in scientific profiles may provide additional granularity when analyzing collaboration behavior between countries (cf. Luukkonen et al., 1992; Okubo et al., 1992).

To our knowledge, this is the first study that quantifies the bilateral collaboration behavior and applies this scheme to study the collaboration patterns between Taiwan and NSP target countries. Future research should consider % of students as well as % of migrants from NSP target countries in Taiwan as potential explanatory factors for the perceived collaboration pattern. Given the considerable budget invested in and resources required for international collaboration, policymakers should be well-informed of the cross-specialization profiles of both countries and their collaboration patterns to make better decisions.

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